

POLICY BRIEF

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IS AI SUPREMACY THE RIGHT PATH TO ENSURE CYBER-SECURITY?*

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POLICY STATEMENT

Artificial intelligence (AI), or behind this branding name, Machine Learning (ML), is a disruptive technology. AI is the technology for big data, specially designed and fitted to extract information from a large amount of data. AI is said to be the next economy, more extensive than the car industry. However, its fast adoption is not without consequences. Like every new technology, it comes with benefits and threats (internal and external). AI itself creates specific categories of threats, such as the "deepfake" and bots' propaganda used for disinformation campaigns. The utilization of AI is also subject to cyber threats, as malevolent actors can mitigate its intrinsic learning abilities.

The European Union's situation on the world stage is behind other competitors. However, European leaders acknowledge the importance of having an ambitious strategy to reach AI global competitors and ensure AI sovereignty and thus citizen protection.

But are the measures efficient enough to protect citizens, and is this the right path after all?

BACKGROUND

By 2030, the AI economy could represent €13 trillion of the global economy (1) and will change society. To be more accurate, AI is not only one technology, but it encompasses different technologies or techniques. They have entered all aspects of our everyday life, from smart assistants, self-driving cars, communications, medical diagnostics, chatbots, to satellites. It has the potential to transform and empower humans in all their sectors of activities. Indeed, AI with big data can help devise solutions to many of society's problems. We can expect, in the following years, research breakthroughs that will accentuate these changes. Between all these aspects, AI plays an increasing role in cybersecurity on both sides: the defense and the attacks, with new techniques.

AI threats can be split into three categories (2): Cyber-attack enhancement, Adversarial Machine Learning (attacking AI), and Specific AI threats (fakes).

Usual cyber-attack techniques could be enhanced by using AI. For example, phishing is not targeted, and the text is generic. Data should be gathered to attack one specific person (spear phishing) with a more realistic email, and it takes time (days-months). AI eliminates the tradeoff for spear phishing. First, it helps find the best targets based on useful personal/public information (data mining and

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machine learning prediction capabilities). To improve social engineering, it will also help gather demographics, compromising data, and any other relevant information to approach the victim. Then it would be fooling the recipient. To differentiate the true from the fake, it would be possible only by adding security checks performed by the machine, not humans.

AI can be used for attacks, but AI-based technologies could be attacked too. The learning process or the data (provided by database or sensors) could be corrupted. As AI is powering more and more new technologies, these attacks become more relevant. They are classified by their nature as follows (3): Poisoning: attackers alter the data used for model training. Evasion: the input data are forged or selected to bypass (evade) the proper classification. This could be particularly dangerous in autonomous vehicles. Machine Learning is also used to forge these data. Stealing: during the training, the data are transferred from servers to the AI software, and the deduced model parameters are also transferred. During these transfers, data or the parameters can be stolen (like medical diagnostics).

By Specific AI threats, we define all the threats using analytic and generative capacities that do not have other kinds of software like synthetic data: text, voice, high-quality images, and videos. They are used to generate fake news. According to the European Network Information Security Agency (ENISA) (4), nation-state-sponsored actors are increasing AI forged information (deep-fakes) to promote cyber-attacks against the election and human rights. Their targets are our society, our elections, and, therefore, our democracy. Moreover, this threat is not limited to the content; it is more deceitful. It is also the way it is propagated and reaches the public (5).

With machine learning, many parameters can be extracted from the public behavior on the internet, for instance, from social media or consumption sites. This internet footprint is called psychographic profiles. It can be political tendencies: conservator, liberals, supported causes, or personal data: family situation and religion. During the 2016 US Presidential Election, Cambridge Analytica claimed to have psychographic profiles of all the 220 million adults in the United States (6). By exploiting this information, propaganda messages were adjusted to each voter profile. Thus, they could trigger specific voter feelings and make them more receptive and politically active. Another way to influence the public is based on the psychological effect of the "echo chamber" (6). Bots play a significant role in this technique by refracting any information comforting a specific belief, thus creating a deformation of reality by amplifying this particular view. AI helps these bots to tailor and target their message according to the public. During the French presidential election in 2017, a campaign on Twitter, Facebook tried to discredit E. Macron with fake generated "leaks" (7).

On the other hand, AI could be used for general cybersecurity purposes: to defend directly, to do forensics, or make security tests. Nowadays, multiple firms are selling AI/Machine Learning solutions for cybersecurity. Also, multiple techniques are devised to avoid data manipulation, evasion, and stealing. Research is ongoing in all these fields, especially identifying the AI potential weakness ahead to implement adequate security measures. AI is also used against all attacks where AI itself is involved. Deep-fake videos are realistic, thus hard to distinguish for ordinary people. Researchers invested in technologies for detecting these generative models (8; 9).

These AI weaknesses and threats are exploited by many countries but not necessarily directly (like spying) to avoid political conflicts. Most cyber-attacks are perpetrated by criminal organizations (60% of all attacks during 2019-2020) (10). Among them, we should mention the "Advanced Persistent Threat" (APT) (11), which are state-sponsored groups. The suspected states behind the most active

APTs are China, Iran, North Korea, and Russia. APTs can be considered as modern privateers. These APT groups are well organized, extremely efficient, and can use any available attack vectors, including AI solutions.

FINDINGS

In the past, only a few actors were active. Today, multiple countries are entering the race for AI supremacy, or at least, as stated by the EU in its white paper, for AI sovereignty.

Compared to its main competitors, China and the USA, the European Union was a fragmented market with different strategies and legislations, and behind in AI development. China is the strongest in academic research (more publications), and the USA has a clear culture of startups and academia-corporate research. Both have tech giants, GAFAM (Google, Apple, Facebook, Amazon et Microsoft; USA) and BATX (Baidu, Alibaba, Tencent and Xiaomi; China), and in both cases, these tech companies matured in their vast and strongly integrated domestic market and even protected in the case of China. The EU has many skills (higher specific formation), a heavy automated industry but has only a few promising startups. To remain competitive and ensure its cybersecurity, the EU has to fill the gap against China and the USA.

Since 2016, the EU digital landscape has been changing quickly and accelerated by the Covid-19 pandemic. In a nutshell, policies on both cybersecurity and AI have evolved in parallel. In 2016 the first EU-wide law on cybersecurity, the Directive on Security of Network and Information Systems (NIS Directive) (12), and, in December 2020, a revised Directive was proposed (NIS2) (13). In April 2018, the workshop report "The European AI Landscape" was published; the same month, 25 European countries signed a "Declaration of cooperation on Artificial Intelligence (AI)" (14), and still the same year, AI fundings were established. In March 2020, an important update was done with the publication of the "White Paper" on Artificial Intelligence (15), and in April 2021, the Commission introduced the "Coordinated Plan On Artificial Intelligence 2021 Review" (16) and the "Artificial Intelligence Act" (17).

The commission strategy for AI is to reduce EU fragmentation by creating a single market for data and technologies. It has invited all Member States as well as Norway and Switzerland to foster the development and use of AI in Europe. Moreover, the Commission aims to coordinate European and national efforts on AI." Presently all member states have adopted a national strategy (18). The commissions also created AI research excellence centers and the national hubs which directly answer the Silicon Valley or the Chinese "AI Innovation and Development Zone." The allocated budget for research and applications is €1.5 billion. It is less than its direct competitors. China's budget is estimated between \$2 to 8.4 billion (19), and the USA budget is \$5.9 billion. But the Commission expected to attract more funds from private investments.

The AI strategy about cybersecurity is defined in accordance with the NIS directive and the "General Data Protection Regulation" (GDPR) and detailed in "Report on the safety and liability implications of Artificial Intelligence, the Internet of Things and robotics" (20). However, they do not impose specific sets of measures or defined standards, except for biometric identification. The directive mentioned only the responsibility to take "adequate" measures: data sets used to train AI systems should be protected; keeping accurate records of training and testing the AI system; proactively providing

adequate information about the use of high-risk AI systems; AI systems can adequately deal with errors and are resilient against both overt attacks and subtle manipulation; implementing validations of AI systems by humans. This is a new approach for cyber-security. As AI has no defined output like a usual program and can not be tested in the same way, each business should determine the necessary measures for its own AI application.

Summarizing, the EU commission strategy focuses on (21; 22; 23): "Placing Europe ahead" of technological developments and encourage the uptake of AI by the public and private sectors, preparing for socio-economic changes brought by AI, ensuring an ethical and legal framework, and creating an "Ecosystem of Trust" with requirements that high-risk AI systems be transparent, traceable, and under human control. The NIS framework imposes that the essential business using AI systems should be resilient against cyber-attacks, and the GDPR imposes resistance against data "stealing". In December 2020, both the Council and the Commission urged to protect democracy against disinformation. The Commission in "European Democracy Action Plan: making EU democracies stronger" states the EU should improve its toolbox to counter foreign interference.

CONCLUSIONS

The European Union has defined an ambitious strategy, and its policy measures answer most of the threats, but the technology should mature with deeper research to reach the desired resilience (as defined in NIS and GDPR). Most of the weaknesses of AI are not identified yet, and extensive AI exploitation in our everyday life makes it an easy target for any malevolent group or state with superior technologies. Our democracy is also dependent on AI; we need AI to detect forged pictures or videos and to stop fake news. At the same time, AI allows the production of better-forged fakes.

This is an escalation situation. Indeed, we are in a race to get the most advanced technology to ensure our security (or for certain actors to attack).

RECOMMENDATIONS

The EU's current budget is less than its direct competitors, China and the USA. The EU is only recovering the gap, which is not enough to reach its ambitious AI strategy and security.

From this point of view, to ensure citizens' security, the EU has to allow more funds to lead AI technology development.

The main shortcoming of this option is that this race could not be won. As we saw with other races between countries (space, nuclear), it stopped only when we reached global agreements and cooperation. In all past examples, huge budgets were spent before reaching cooperation. Some people can argue that it stimulated development, but we also have many examples of prolific partnerships (CERN, ITER, etc.). Therefore, it is conceivable to try, since the beginning to seek cooperation instead of race.

"Artificial intelligence is the future, not only for Russia but for all of humankind. It comes with colossal opportunities but also threats that are difficult to predict. Whoever becomes the leader in this sphere

will become the ruler of the world... it would not be very desirable that this monopoly be concentrated in someone's specific hands. That's why, if we become leaders in this area, we will share this know-how with the entire world." Russian President V. Putin, 2017 (24). We cannot be certain that Russia will apply its recommendation, but this citation is interesting because it summarizes the situation.

In June 2020, the Global Partnership on AI (GPAI) was launched to fostering international cooperation on cutting-edge research and applied activities on AI. We recommend pursuing both ways, technological independence and focusing on international cooperation, and sharing technology with less advanced countries. We also want these countries not to get left behind. In the end, our security also depends on their development (25).

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